

An Exploration of Neptune's Dynamical History in Relation to the Classical Kuiper Belt Objects

J. Jackson¹ and R. Murray-Clay¹

Received _____; accepted _____

¹Harvard-Smithsonian Center for Astrophysics, 60 Garden Street, Cambridge, MA 02138

ABSTRACT

The structure of the outer disk of planetesimals in today’s solar system was shaped largely by the dynamical history of Neptune. In the Classical Region of the Kuiper Belt, there exist overlying populations of high-inclination, dynamically hot Kuiper Belt objects (KBOs) and low-inclination cold objects, each with uniquely defined properties. The characteristics of these populations can provide insight into Neptune’s past. To date, there has been no successful simulation of Neptune’s history that scatters the hot KBOs to their observed locations today and preserves the cold population without secularly exciting the objects to eccentricities beyond that of the observational data. However, it has been suggested that if, in Neptune’s migration from its formation location interior to the present-day planet, it experienced a period of high eccentricity, it could scatter some hot objects into the classical region without exciting the cold KBOs to high eccentricities. We explore the eccentricity/semimajor axis parameter space of Neptune in an attempt to find a model that matches the observed data. In our simulations, we provide Neptune with an initial eccentricity and then damp it over relevant timescales to the fairly circular orbit it exhibits today. While the examples we run provide histories of Neptune that support the conservative constraints placed on the hot and cold KBOs, there appears to be no point in our initial parameter space capable of producing a Kuiper Belt that accurately matches that of our current solar system. However, in testing more extreme initial conditions, the resulting classical objects seemed to match their respective observed populations, verifying this model as a possible history of Neptune.

1. Introduction

Neptune’s current orbit is very nearly circular with a semimajor axis around $30AU$ and a low inclination. However, the more chaotic orbits of Pluto and the rest of the Kuiper Belt objects (KBOs) suggest that this may not have always been the case. Neptune’s exact dynamical history is not obvious from observations of the Kuiper Belt, but it is clear that the planet must have experienced some dynamic period in which it shaped the KBOs into four distinct classes. First, a group of objects in mean motion resonance with Neptune; second, a group of objects that are currently being scattered by Neptune; third, a population of dynamically cold classical objects (between about 40 and $50AU$); lastly, a class of dynamically hot classical objects superimposed on the cold population (Gladman et al. 2008). The two populations of classical objects have clear, unique properties such as color (Tegler & Romanishin 2000; Thommes et al. 2002; Peixinho et al. 2008), size (Levison & Stern 2001; Fraser et al. 2010), albedo (Brucker et al. 2009), and binary fraction (Stephens & Noll 2006; Noll et al. 2008).

Past models that provide relevant possibilities for Neptune’s history are all based on the concept of planetesimal-driven migration (Fernandez & Ip 1984). This is a process by which the giant planets move outwards or inward in the planetary disk of the solar system through their interactions with small objects. Neptune, for example, is too small to consistently eject planetesimals from the system, so when it scatters them out, they tend to remain gravitationally bound to the Sun. However, Jupiter and Saturn are massive enough to eject planetesimals. Thus, when an object that has been scattered in by Neptune interacts with Jupiter and leaves the solar system, Neptune gains angular momentum while Jupiter loses it, causing the two planets to migrate in opposite directions. The first model based on this concept, suggested that Neptune was formed approximately $10AU$ closer to the Sun than it is today and migrated outwards on a circular orbit (Malhotra 1993, 1995;

Hahn & Malhotra 2005). The second significant model in the literature has been presented by Levison et al. (2008) and is based on the Nice model (Morbidelli et al. 2008). In Levison’s model, planetesimal-driven migration cause either Jupiter or Saturn to migrate through or break out of mean motion resonance with Neptune. The chaos this created placed Neptune on a highly eccentric orbit that was damped over time.

While these models have provided physical justifications for the resonant and scattering populations of KBOs, astronomers have yet to successfully produce both of the unique classical populations we observe today. Recent publications have suggested that an in situ population of cold objects could be preserved in a variation of the Nice model if Neptune experienced fast apsidal precession (Batygin et al. 2011). However, the physical motivations for fast precession have not been thoroughly examined and may prove to be concerns with this suggestion (Dawson & Murray-Clay 2012). Although some models are able to create all four dynamical classes of KBOs, none to date have successfully achieved results that agree with current-day eccentricity observations of KBO orbits.

Since the publication of these models, broad explorations of Neptune’s parameter space have been conducted. Dawson & Murray-Clay (2012) have successfully ruled out the vast majority of this parameter space, especially focusing on (a, e) space. They suggest that Neptune must have spent some time at a high eccentricity during its migration outwards in order to produce the observed hot population, but that this eccentricity must have damped quickly in order to preserve the cold KBOs. While Dawson & Murray-Clay (2012) provide some example integrations in this parameter space that satisfy the loose constraints they set on the eccentricities of the hot and cold populations, their results fail to produce a cold population that qualitatively matches the observed data and a hot population with eccentricities as low as those observed.

We propose to explore the rest of the remaining (a, e) space through the use of an

N-body integrator with eccentricity damping for Neptune. We will set more rigorous criteria for the hot classical population and attempt to match these criteria through our model. Our integrations could result in either of the following two possibilities: (1) we find a point in (a, e) space that successfully embeds the scattered hot classical population on top of the cold population that developed in situ, while maintaining low eccentricities consistent with the given observational data, or (2) we rule out the idea of a period of high eccentricity in Neptune’s past as the dominant factor in forming the structure of the Kuiper Belt.

Many past models have included all four giant planets in their integrations, along with several thousand massless KBOs, but with such broad simulations, it has been computationally difficult to explore all of parameter space. Additionally, it has been shown that apart from indirect effects from their interactions with Neptune, the other three giant planets show negligible effects on the orbits of the KBOs in the classical region (Wolff et al. 2012). Thus, in our model, we will only include Neptune and the KBOs, but we will provide the integrator with user-defined forces on Neptune’s orbit in order to compensate for the missing giant planets.

In the following section, we will describe the physical processes which our integration will simulate. Section 3 will discuss the N-body integrator used in our calculations and explain our setup in depth. In Section 4, we will discuss the results of our survey of parameter space and additional integrations that we will run. Lastly, in Section 5, we will draw conclusions based on our results and attempt to discern whether or not our model is sufficient to recreate the modern-day Kuiper Belt. Additionally, this section will be used as a medium to suggest methods to expand upon our work.

2. The Story of Neptune’s Past

Our model allows for the concepts described in both the Levison (2008) and Malhotra (1993, 1995) papers in that we begin our integrations at some point after the formation of planets and planetesimals. We start Neptune at one of several semimajor axes interior to its current orbital location, assuming it to be in the midst of its outward migration. Neptune is also provided with varying initial eccentricities in our integrations such that it will be capable of scattering objects to the classical region. This eccentricity will be damped down to near zero over a much shorter timescale than that of Neptune’s outward planetesimal-driven migration.

In addition to Neptune, our solar system model will include a nearly uniform disk of 30,600 planetesimals between 18 and 50AU, distinguished only nominally by their initial location (there will be more planetesimals interior to the classical region because only some small proportion will actually be scattered to that region). However, once particles from the 18-40 AU range make it to the classical region, they will be distinguished from the cold particles in terms of the distinctive properties that come with formation closer to the Sun. These planetesimals all begin with low eccentricities and inclinations and will be considered massless for this model. The initial conditions for an example integration in (a, e) space are shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1.— Example of initial conditions for one of the integrations to be run in Section 4. Here, Neptune (black asterisk) begins with a semimajor axis of 30 AU and an eccentricity of 0.275. Objects that have the potential to scatter into the classical region and become hot classicals are denoted in blue, while objects formed in the classical region (cold classicals) are denoted in red.

Neptune scatters planetesimals in one of two directions: in toward the Sun, or out toward the classical region. Objects that are scattered inwards by Neptune are unlikely to survive long-term due to the same process that allows Neptune’s orbit to migrate: ejection due to the scattering of Jupiter and Saturn. However, objects scattered outwards by Neptune have a much greater chance of survival, as evidenced by the existence of the Kuiper Belt in the present solar system. Thus, we assume that this scattering is the origin of the hot classical population and model it as discussed in the following section.

3. Constructing the Model

In addition to the values mentioned in Section 2, we provide Neptune with initial conditions assuming that it lies directly on the plane of the planetary disk. Since Neptune

and the Sun are the only non-negligible objects in our system, it only makes sense for Neptune’s orbit to be superimposed on the plane. Thus, the following initial conditions were chosen for Neptune:

$$\text{Mass} = M_{\text{Neptune}}$$

$$\text{Inclination} = 0$$

$$\text{Argument of Pericenter} = 0$$

$$\text{Longitude of Ascending Node} = 0$$

$$\text{Mean Anomaly} = 0$$

In addition to Neptune and the Sun, our solar system model will include about 30,000 massless test particles that will serve as our planetesimal disk. The unique properties of the hot and cold populations of classical objects discussed in Section 1 suggest that the hot particles were formed interior to the cold particles (Dawson & Murray-Clay 2012). Thus, for our integrations, we place 30,000 particles at random initial semi-major axes between 18 and 40*AU* (hot population) and 600 particles at initial semi-major axes between 40 and 50*AU* (cold population). Once the integrations are complete, we will zoom in to the 40 – 50*AU* area and observe the hot particles that have scattered there as well as the cold particles that were placed there in situ. We also give them the following relevant initial conditions:

$$\text{Eccentricity} = \text{random number between } 0 \text{ and } 0.02$$

$$\text{Inclination} = \text{random angle between } 0^\circ \text{ and } 1.0^\circ$$

$$\text{Argument of Pericenter} = \text{random angle between } 0 \text{ and } 2\pi \text{ radians}$$

$$\text{Longitude of Ascending Node} = \text{random angle between } 0 \text{ and } 2\pi \text{ radians}$$

Mean Anomaly = random angle between 0 and 2π radians

With the initial parameters set, we use the *Mercury* 6.2 hybrid symplectic integrator (Chambers 1999), an N-body code which allows for massless particles, to integrate Neptune’s orbit over time. While the remaining three giant planets are left out of this integration, their effects on Neptune are accounted for through the use of fictitious, user-defined forces that precess Neptune’s orbit. In our integrations, Neptune’s eccentricity is damped from its initial point to its current value of approximately 0. This damping may occur through dynamical friction from the disk of planetesimals as well as resonant relaxation (Tremaine 1998).

While we model these planetesimals as massless objects, we recognize that, in reality, the planetary disk applies a force on Neptune. Thus, we apply compensational forces that modify Neptune’s semimajor axis a_N , eccentricity e_N , and inclination i_N . In agreement with the models of Malhotra (1993), Levison et al. (2008), and Wolff et al. (2012), we use the following functional forms:

$$e_N = e_0 * \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\tau_e}\right) * i_N = i_0 * \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\tau_i}\right) \quad (1)$$

$$a_N = a_f + (a_0 - a_f) * \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\tau_a}\right), \quad (2)$$

Where a_0 is the initial semimajor axis of Neptune, $a_f = 30AU$ is the final semimajor axis, and τ_e , τ_i , and τ_a are the damping timescales for eccentricity, inclination, and semimajor axis, respectively. For our integrations, Neptune’s inclination will start at 0, so it will not be damped. However, it has been shown that the damping of eccentricity and inclination can be treated independently in this case (Wolff et al. 2012).

In determining which initial conditions we should run our integrations with, we first

turn to the observational data on the classical planetesimals in our solar system. Figure 2 shows the populations of hot and cold classicals with the conservative constraints placed on their eccentricity by Dawson & Murray-Clay (2012). The entire population of cold classicals is confined to a maximum eccentricity of 1.0 in the region between 42.5 and 45AU. The curve in the right panel marks the boundary where $q = 34AU$, the upper limit for long-term survival, where q is the distance at pericenter (Dawson & Murray-Clay 2012). For our integrations to be successful, some of the scattered hot objects must lie below this boundary.

Fig. 2.— Observed eccentricity distributions of objects in the classical region plotted over the survival rate maps of Lykawka & Mukai (2005). The cold classicals (left) are defined as objects with $i < 2$ and the hot objects (right) are defined by $i > 6$. The solid yellow line plots $e = 0.1$ and places an upper boundary on the cold classicals between 42.5 and 45AU. The dotted line which plots periaapse $q = 34AU$ places a boundary on the long-term survival of planetesimals in this region. Classical objects are taken from the Minor Planet Center Database and the CanadaFrance Ecliptic Plane Survey (CFEPS; Kavelaars et al. 2009) and are classified by Gladman et al. (2008), Kavelaars et al. (2009), and Volk & Malhotra (2011). The full figure has been taken from Dawson & Murray-Clay (2012).

We focus on the planetesimals that are scattered out by Neptune. The observational data in Figure 2 shows that some scattered hot planetesimals exist in the classical region today, below the survival boundary defined by Dawson & Murray-Clay (2012). Unlike the scattered hot particles, the cold particles experience secular evolution, maintaining a constant semimajor axis, but increasing in eccentricity and inclination for as long as Neptune remains in its period of heightened eccentricity (Wolff et al. 2012).

We choose initial integration conditions based on the parameter space plot shown in Figure 3. This figure rules out most of (a, e) space, but we explore the remaining section in the high semimajor axis, high eccentricity corner, which includes maximum damping timescale values. We choose 8 representative points in on this plot and run integrations with the appropriate a_N , e_N , and τ_e in search of results in which the cold particles stay below the constraint set in Figure 2, while the hot particles scatter to eccentricities low enough to lie on top of the cold population. A table of the points in parameter space chosen for our integrations can be found in Section 4.

Fig. 3.— Combined constraints on cold and hot classical populations in (a, e) space. The hot particles, confined by their ability to scatter to the classical region and below the curve defined in Figure 1, prevent Neptune’s high-eccentricity period from occurring in the red striped area. The cold particles, confined by an upper boundary in eccentricity caused by secular evolution, present maximum eccentricity damping timescales for Neptune. This plot is taken from Dawson & Murray-Clay (2012).

4. Results

The integrations we perform will bring one of two results: (1) we discover a point in parameter space that scatters hot particles to low enough eccentricities in the classical region, while maintaining the dynamically cold population, or (2) we rule out a period of high eccentricity of Neptune as the driving force resulting in the current structure of the Kuiper Belt.

Figure 4 shows the parameter space constraints on Neptune described in Figure 3, with points plotted for each of the eight integrations run in this study. These points were chosen in an attempt to be fully representative of all of the remaining (a, e) space. Points were chosen with the understanding that a high damping timescale would scatter more hot particles to the region of interest, but a low damping timescale would have less difficulty maintaining the cold population. Typical dynamical solar system models are run for $4Gyr$ in order to test the long-term stability of the system on relevant timescales. However, as shown in Figure 2, the constraints we have set on the KBOs already account for survival rate. Thus, we can focus solely on the high-eccentricity period of interest and run our integrations for $1Myr$. Table 1 shows the parameters of Neptune that were used for each integration.

Fig. 4.— This image shows the parameter space plot described in Figure 3, over-plotted with the initial conditions used in our integrations. Each of the points is labeled with an integration number from Table 1.

The observational data on current KBOs is plotted in Figure 5 along with the constraints placed by Dawson & Murray-Clay on the cold population discussed in Figure 2. Using Figure 5, it is clear that the constraint set on the hot population, while consistent with long-term survival rates, is far too conservative to fit the actual data. In order for our model to be considered successful, the hot particles must fit with the stricter criterion that some objects must fall below the $q = 39.5AU$ line. This line is plotted over the Dawson & Murray-Clay (2012) graph.

Fig. 5.— Plotted are the observed results of the current KBOs in (a, e) space. The blue points plot the hot population based on the criteria discussed in Figure 1. The cold population is plotted in red. Over-plotted on this graph is the constraint placed on the cold population that $e < 0.1$ for $42.5 < a < 45AU$ as well as the new criterion for the hot population ($q > 39.5AU$).

In using the maximum timescales given by Figure 3, all of our results fit the constraints set on the hot and cold populations by Dawson and Murray-Clay (2012). However, there is a clear distinction in the hot particles that can be seen with increasing semimajor axis. The three integrations in which Neptune was given a semimajor axis below $28.5AU$ showed limited success in achieving hot particles below the highly conservative $q = 34AU$ boundary. A representative example can be seen in Figure 6. The damping time used in the integration was determined by the contours in Figure 3. Here, we start with initial conditions similar

Table 1. Integration Parameters for each Integration

Integration #	Semimajor Axis (AU)	Eccentricity	Eccentricity Damping (Myrs)
1	26	0.38	0.33
2	28.5	0.33	0.25
3	27	0.30	0.20
4	28.5	0.23	0.33
5	30	0.24	0.24
6	30	0.275	0.14
7	26.5	0.23	0.33
8	30	0.35	0.07

Note. — Values here indicate Neptune’s initial parameters for each integration. The reasoning for these choices will be explained in Section 5.

to those shown in Figure 1, and then zoom in on the classical region after the scattering takes place.

Fig. 6.— Example of a less successful integration (Integration 1). This is a plot of semimajor axis vs. eccentricity for all the particles in the classical region at the last timestep of the integration ($t = 1Myr$). The initial parameters of Neptune for this integration were: $a_N = 26AU$, $e_N = 0.38$, and $\tau_e = 0.33Myr$. Hot particles are plotted in blue while cold particles are plotted in red. The yellow line indicates a maximum value for the eccentricities of cold particles. Hot particles above the line $q = 34AU$ are plotted with fainter points, indicating their long-term instability. Only a few hot planetesimals would be capable of survival in this scenario.

Figure 7 presents a representative example of our more successful results ($a \geq 28.5AU$). Here, more successful describes integration results that show the lowest eccentricities in the scattered hot population, well below the $q = 34AU$ curve. While this figure shows a plot of Integration 6, Integrations 2, 5, and 8 showed similar success in scattering the hot classicals to low eccentricity.

Fig. 7.— Example of an integration in the more successful class in which $a_N > 28.5AU$ (Integration 6). Similar to Figure 6, this image plots the hot (blue) and cold (red) particles in the classical region at the conclusion of the integration while clarifying the $q = 34AU$ line, below which hot KBOs can survive. The initial parameters for this integration were: $a_N = 30AU$, $e_N = 0.275$, and $\tau_e = 0.14Myr$.

While our "more successful" integrations fit well with the constraints set by Dawson & Murray-Clay (2012), they fail to meet the stricter requirement described above where $q > 39.5AU$ for some hot particles. This is evidenced by Figure 8 which displays the results of Figures 6 and 7, but lowers the hot classical boundary to our new curve. None of the integrations discussed thus far are capable of meeting this requirement. This result will be examined further in Section 5.

Fig. 8.— Example integrations shown in Figures 6 (left) and 7 (right) with stricted constraints on the orbital location of the hot particles. Neither integration places any blue objects below the $q = 39.5AU$ line.

Let us now consider the scattering analytically. Since Neptune only scatters objects that are within its Hill radius, the hot objects in the classical region must have pericenters within a Hill radius of some point on Neptune’s orbit. This is because the point of scattering becomes the minimum orbital radius of objects that are scattered outwards, as per Figure 9. This allows us to know that the largest pericenter of hot objects in the classical region must be less than or equal the radius of Neptune at apogee plus the Hill radius:

$$q_{max} = a_N(1 + e_{N,max}) + a_N(1 - e_{N,max})\sqrt[3]{\frac{m_N}{3M_{sun}}} \quad (3)$$

Calculating the Hill radius of Neptune for our best results, we get:

$$r_{Hill} = a_N(1 - e_{N,max})\sqrt[3]{\frac{m_N}{3M_{sun}}} = (30AU)(1 - 0.275)\sqrt[3]{\frac{5.15 * 10^5}{3(1)}} = 0.561AU \quad (4)$$

This results in a maximum pericenter line of $q = 38.561AU$ which is below the

minimum pericenter needed to meet our stricter criterion for hot particles. In Figure 10, we plot this curve over our results from integration 6.

Fig. 9.— Diagram that shows the initial disk of planetesimals (left) and the result of Neptune scattering a particle outwards while at apogee (right). The planetesimal disk is represented in gray, Neptune is denoted by the blue circle, the Sun is denoted by the yellow circle, and the orbit of the scattered object is denoted by the black ellipse.

Fig. 10.— Plotted over the image from Figure 8 (right panel) is the maximum pericenter line calculated using Equation 3.

Given the fact that none of the parameters chosen for our integrations except for integration 8 result in a maximum pericenter for hot KBOs above $39.5AU$, we attempt two more simulations in which we go beyond the parameter space suggested in Figure 3 in order to achieve a splash of hot particles below the criterion that was set. These last two integrations have eccentricities above 0.4, allowing the maximum pericenter line to fall and include the locations in parameter space of our observed hot particles. Since our goal is to place scattered hot objects below the $39.5AU$ pericenter line and the pericenter of these particles is equivalent to the point of scattering, we alter our assumptions slightly to start the hot objects between 18 and $42AU$. Table 2 presents the parameters for these last two integrations as well as their maximum pericenter lines.

Integration 9 was unsuccessful in that the cold particles were too excited by the increased eccentricity of Neptune. This result can be seen in Figure 11. Integration 10,

however, was successful in producing some hot particles in the observed region. These results are plotted in Figure 12 and will be discussed in further detail in Section 5.

Fig. 11.— Plot of the cold particles of Integration 9 which break the eccentricity constraint set by Dawson & Murray-Clay (2012), marked by the yellow line.

Table 2. Integration Parameters for Additional Integrations

Integration #	Semimajor Axis (AU)	Eccentricity	Eccentricity Damping Myrs	Maximum Pericenter AU
9	30	0.425	0.04	43.195
10	28.5	0.5	0.05	43.118

Fig. 12.— Results of Integration 10. The distinction between small and large blue dots represents the stricter criterion for hot particles discussed above. Also overplotted on this image is the eccentricity restriction on cold particles and the maximum pericenter line from Table 2.

5. Discussion

Through a thorough study of Neptune’s (a, e) space during a period of high eccentricity, presented by Dawson & Murray-Clay (2012), we suggest that there are no points in this parameter space which produce results similar to the observed Kuiper Belt data. Thus, a period of eccentricity between 0.25 and 0.35 in Neptune does not appear to be capable of singularly dominating the formation of the present-day structure of the classical region. Thus, our results suggest that the model of Dawson & Murray-Clay does not seem feasible within the parameter space presented.

The eight initial points on the parameter space plot shown in Figure 4 were chosen in an attempt to garner a complete understanding of the remaining space that was capable

of producing the hot and cold populations of planetesimals in the outer disk. Points were chosen either to maximize or minimize damping time in specific regions of space on that plot. The parameter space did not include eccentricities or semimajor axes beyond those shown in Figure 3 because it was believed that (1) eccentricity damping that quickly would be difficult to produce in a physical universe, and (2) this damping would be incapable of scattering enough hot particles to the classical region before Neptune’s orbit was no longer eccentric. This will be discussed in further detail below.

All of the results of our initial integrations seemed to pass the constraints set on the hot and cold populations in Figure 2 (Dawson & Murray-Clay 2012); however, these constraints were rather conservative. In our results, we looked for some hot particles in the classical region to have eccentricities matching those of the observational data ($q > 39.5AU$). Said eccentricities were not observed in any of our initial results. This observation was supported by Equation 3, which showed that our models were incapable of scattering hot particles to low enough eccentricities because Neptune’s orbital radius at apogee was not far enough away from the Sun.

A concern with using the maximum pericenter lines as indicators of where hot particles would end up was that in the same way secular evolution can cause eccentricity to rise in low-eccentricity particles, it could have caused the hot particles to decrease in eccentricity such that they fell below the pericenter lines. After plotting these lines over our results, it became clear that we could discuss the situation in terms of pericenter lines, a significant discovery in that it allows us to consider the model analytically, not just numerically.

After examining the (a, e) space presented in Figure 3 and determining that these initial conditions would not result in the structure of the Kuiper Belt we observe today, we chose to attempt a more drastic model with a smaller damping timescale. While Integration 9 was unsuccessful in maintaining the low eccentricity cold population, Integration 10

demonstrated cold particles well below the constraint (even so much as to qualitatively match the observed population). Most importantly, although there is a gap in the hot particles that comes from resonance with Neptune, this population definitively meets our criterion for "matching the observed data."

One concern when dealing with such extreme values for Neptune's eccentricity is that there are few physical motivations for this. However, one possible explanation is that in the same way Neptune scatters planetesimals, Neptune itself could have been kicked out to a high apocenter by another giant planet and then scattered back in shortly thereafter. This scenario would account for both the extreme apocenter and the short timescale during which Neptune can remain there. Thus, we have found a possible history of Neptune that cannot be ruled out based on Kuiper Belt observations.

While fast eccentricity damping of Neptune initially seemed the most viable history to create the current structure of KBOs, our results suggest that other histories must be explored. Fast apsidal precession has been suggested as an alternative method (Batygin et al. 2011; Dawson & Murray-Clay 2012). It was discussed in Section 1 that the physical reasoning behind such fast precession raises concerns; however, without testing these physical motivations, it cannot be ruled out as an option. Thus, it would be worth experimenting to find how quickly Neptune's orbit can precess while maintaining the cold population. Likewise, in the future it would be helpful to explore the more extreme regions of Neptune's (a, e) space in an attempt to match the observed KBO data as well as possible.

Our results suggest that the model of high eccentricity with a fast damping rate is incapable of producing the structure of the Kuiper Belt within the confines of the parameter space suggested by Dawson & Murray-Clay. However, we have discovered that the desired results can be achieved by creating a greater maximum pericenter line for hot particles by providing Neptune with the parameters necessary for an apocenter near $43AU$.

6. Acknowledgements

A special thanks to Doug Finkbeiner and the Astronomy 98 class for helping through this project every step of the way.

REFERENCES

- (1) Batygin, K., Brown, M. E., & Fraser, W. C. 2011, *The Astrophysical Journal*
- (2) Brucker, M. J., Grundy, W. M., Stansberry, J. A., et al. 2009, *Icarus*
- (3) Dawson, R. I. & Murray-Clay, R. 2012, *The Astrophysical Journal*
- (4) Fernandez, J. A. & Ip, W.-H. 1984, *Icarus*
- (5) Fraser, W. C., Brown, M. E., & Schwamb, M. E. 2010, *Icarus*
- (6) Gladman, B., Marsden, B. G., & Vanlaerhoven, C. 2008, *The Solar System beyond Neptune*, ed. M. A. Barucci, H. Boehnhardt, D. P. Cruikshank, & A. Morbidelli (Tucson, AZ: Univ. Arizona Press)
- (7) Hahn, J. M., & Malhotra, R. 2005, *The Astronomical Journal*
- (8) Kavelaars, J. J., Jones, R. L., Gladman, B. J., et al. 2009, *The Astronomical Journal*
- (9) Levison, H. F., Morbidelli, A., Vanlaerhoven, C., Gomes, R., & Tsiganis, K. 2008, *Icarus*
- (10) Levison, H. F., & Stern, S. A. 2001, *The Astronomical Journal*
- (11) Lykawka, P. S. & Mukai, T. 2005, *Earth Moon Planets*
- (12) Malhotra, R. 1993, *Nature*
- (13) Malhotra, R. 1995, *The Astronomical Journal*
- (14) Morbidelli, A., Levison, H. F., & Gomes, R. 2008, *The Solar System beyond Neptune*, ed. M. A. Barucci, H. Boehnhardt, D. P. Cruikshank, & A. Morbidelli (Tucson, AZ: Univ. Arizona Press)

- (15) Noll, K. S., Grundy, W. M., Stephens, D. C., Levison, H. F., & Kern, S. D. 2008, *Icarus*
- (16) Peixinho, N., Lacerda, P., & Jewitt, D. 2008, *The Astronomical Journal*
- (17) Stephens, D. C., & Noll, K. S. 2006, *The Astronomical Journal*
- (18) Tegler, S. C., & Romanishin, W. 2000, *Nature*
- (19) Thommes, E. W., Duncan, M. J., & Levison, H. F. 2002, *The Astronomical Journal*
- (20) Volk, K. & Malhotra, R. 2011, *The Astrophysical Journal*
- (21) Wolff, S., Dawson, R. I., & Murray-Clay, R. A. 2012, *The Astrophysical Journal*